

SURVIVING COVID-19: IMPLICATIONS ON THE MAGNA CARTA FOR PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS HEALTH MEASURES, PROVISIONS, AND MANAGEMENT

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Surviving Covid-19: Implications on the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers Health Measures, Provisions, and Management

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Abstract

Academic year 2020-2021 was a challenging time to work in public-school in Philippines. Coronavirus Disease of 2019 (Covid-19) became a global outbreak. Governments around the world issued protocols to mitigate the spread of the virus including the Department of Education (DepEd). On July 1, 2020, DepEd has adopted the modular distance learning as an alternative to the classroom set up. Distribution of modules to students was the best option to ensure that learning continues amidst the outbreak. This study is a primary data analysis of qualitative responses collected to evaluate the conditions of public-school teachers who tested positive of Covid-19. The lived experiences of ten (8) teachers across three (3) School Divisions in Luzon region were captured through open-ended interviews as the teachers continued to render their services in their respective stations. A phenomenological study was conducted to discover their health and mental conditions during and after contracting the disease. A thematic framework was used to organize the results of the data from the interview conducted through alternative platform (ZOOM). Findings showed that public school teachers remained in their jobs notwithstanding the stress and anxiety triggered by fear of looming a virus which eventually led to them contracting the virus. Implications for discussions of policies under the Magna Carta for Teachers is recommended to ensure full recovery from “long haul Covid-19” a further deterioration of their physical and mental health.

Keywords: *corona virus disease (covid-19), qualitative response, magna carta for teachers, deped, long haul covid*

Introduction

Teaching is the noblest profession because transfer of knowledge will be impaired. In order to continuously improve the educational system, healthy teachers are needed to maintain a happy environment in the classroom. Thus, public school teachers are vital stakeholders of the country’s public education system. They cater to the millions of Filipino students whose desire of getting at least a basic education has been clinging on the government’s support for its realization. For that reason, the government must ensure that public school teachers are given priority on their interest, security and health welfare to the optimum.

At the outset Republic Act 4670 otherwise known as the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers declaration of policy states that this Act promotes and improves the social and economic status of public-school teachers, their living and working conditions, as cited in Section 1. It is observed by the researcher that the health conditions of the teacher are not mentioned. Furthermore, Article IV, Section 22 of the same Act considers Health Measures and Injury Benefits of public teachers, to wit: “Compulsory medical examination shall be provided free of charge for all the teachers before they take up teaching and shall be repeated not less than once a year during the teacher’s professional life.” On the other hand, section 23 states that “Teachers shall be protected against the consequences of employment injuries in accordance with existing laws.

Corona Virus Disease otherwise known as COVID-19 emerged in year 2019 in China. On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization declared the corona virus outbreak a global public health emergency. This has immensely shaken the academic arena. It has disrupted learning and education of an estimated eight hundred ninety-seven (897) million students all over the world. It has brought drastic changes and challenges to the global education community. (Huang, et. al., 2020). Teachers, as educational frontliners felt its impact with regard to their instructional duties. In the work of Carisen, et. al. (2020), teachers’ experiences, obstacles and opportunities were narrated that while everyone is facing uncertainty, educators’ duties are still bound to the consideration of equity, inclusivity and the importance of access for all learners. This massive challenge in educational setting prompts the Department of Education, Department of Health and the Office of the President to issue directives, policy-guidelines underscoring the Department of Health’s announcement placing the entire Philippines under COVID-19 Alert System to Code Red Sublevel-1 as well as President Rodrigo R. Duterte’s agreement to declare a State of Public Health Emergency (DM No. 034, S. 2020, dated 03/09/2020).

In the light of COVID-19 Pandemic, DEPED Offices and Schools are instructed to ensure that all public and private schools’ personnel, teachers and learners who are known to have had close contacts with confirmed cases of COVID-19 shall undergo home quarantine and reiterates the quarantine requirement as enumerated in Department Memorandum 031, S. 2020 must remain.

COVID-19 Pandemic is phenomenal, the fact that the virus is invisible, and it harms anybody, it causes every teacher, learner and parents as well to be in emotional and psychological distress. The sudden shift of all public school system from face-to-face classroom setting to distance learning with variety of learning modalities led the public-school teachers to a difficult and stressful condition. Public schools in remote areas do not have access to good internet connectivity hence they have to adapt the use of modules in hardcopy. The teachers are obliged to write modules with matching lesson plans, take charge of encoding, printing and distribution or issuance to parents. Those activities performed by the public-school teachers in compliance to the mandate of the Civil Service Commission as

facilitators of learning put them to a very risky situation of having exposed to symptomatic and asymptomatic COVID-19 positive people.

In line with the observations of the researcher, she was prompted to investigate and study the possible health risk faced by the teachers. She wanted to find out if education frontlines are in good state of health physically, emotionally and mentally while in active service, hence this study about the lived experiences of public-school teachers in Antipolo City, a beautiful spot in the province of Rizal.

Research Questions

There has been no research conducted on the lived experiences of teachers in the public schools who were found COVID-19 positive, so far, as of this writing. This boosted the interest of the researcher to conduct research that answered these research questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of the public-school teachers who recovered from COVID-19 during the year 2020-2021?
2. How do the participants of the study describe their physical, emotional and mental conditions while in the process of medication during and after treatment period?
3. How did the respondents cope with Covid19?
4. How did the respondents describe their state of being after they survived Covid19?
5. What intervention can be recommended by this study that can mitigate the health crisis brought by COVID-19 pandemic?

Literature Review

The global expansion of the COVID-19 Pandemic Disease has caused the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare a public health emergency last January 30, 2020). Within a short span of the COVID-19 outbreak many researchers have shared their works on health issues, protocols and far-reaching changes in all aspects of lives of people all over the world, like education, economy, socio-cultural and health care programs across regions.

In the study conducted by Rabacal, Oducado and Tamdang, they determined the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality of life (QoL) of professional teachers in the Philippines. The results indicated a moderate COVID-19 impact on the QoL of the teachers, however, the presence of a COVID-19 case near the teacher's residence, death due to COVID-19 in their community and school, the prevalence of medical conditions among COVID-19 patients were perceived as big threat to them.

According to the study of Dryhurst, et.al., (2020) people's personal experience with the virus and hearing about the virus from friends and family significantly predicted risk perception. Also, the perception of threat and risk from COVID-19 were found to influence negative mental states and emotions in the study of Kim and Perez, 2020. These findings are similar to the findings of the present study based on the answer of the teacher-participants that they experienced serious mental distress while recuperating from the infection. Most of the eight (8) teachers experienced depression, homesick during the quarantine period in the facility, mental stress, extreme loneliness, trauma and grief.

Sederdahl and Williams (2020), Donostia – San Sebastian, Spain published material about psychology and mental health of teachers during COVID-19 pandemic supported the responses of the teacher-participants in the current study that: (a) teachers have been affected by the enhanced community quarantine (ECQ) or lockdown with respect to mental health, (b) relationships in three (3) main fields i.e., work, family and social relationships, (c) higher levels of distress due to the work load generated during ECQs and GCQs.

Zhou et.al., (2017); Navis (2018), Wang et.al, (2020) described loneliness as behavioral epidemic, it is associated with various physical and mental repercussions, including elevated systolic blood pressure and increased risk for heart disease. Both loneliness and social isolation (brought about by forced quarantine during lockdowns) have been associated with an increased risk for coronary heart disease associated to death.

Methodology

Research Design

The fundamental principle of the phenomenological approach is that the researcher must remain true to the facts and how they reveal themselves (Husserl, 1960). To achieve this, Descriptive Phenomenological Method is perfectly suitable as the research design of this study because this recognizes the fact that a person is a historical being and his experiences are part of a man's wholeness. The aim of a study is to arrive at meanings explication is used to reveal the phenomena under question. Within the method of explication, one tries to understand the actual context within which the facts emerge (Giorgi, 1970).

Participants

The researcher is an educational practitioner, a special education teacher in status, with guidance counseling as her major field, has acquired eight (8) colleagues in the school division of Rizal/Manila and Antipolo City. The eight (8) teacher-participants were the subjects or respondents of the current study. The participants of the study were the public-school teachers who recovered from COVID-19, they were tested positive at a certain period during school year 2020-2021.

Instruments

The researcher utilized semi-structured interview via video calls on Google Meet with guide open-ended questions allowing for a discussion with the interviewee rather than a straightforward question and answer format. Open-ended questions asked to all participants in the same sequence with similar follow-up questions and probes. Building Rapport was a key element in the success of the interview. The instrument used in the interview was validated by an expert recommended by the educational institution for which this research adheres to.

Data Procedure

The letter requests prior to the conduct of the study were sent to three (3) School Divisions namely SDO Antipolo, SDO Rizal and SDO Manila. Approval was received through email. Letter of consent was sent and received through email to and from each participant in the study. Video recordings from the interview were then transcribed verbatim and was sent back to the participants for confirmation and authentication.

Ethical Considerations

Before starting the study by collaborating with the respondents, the researcher went over and explained the objective of the study. Along with a letter encouraging respondents to complete the necessary questionnaire voluntarily and thoroughly, the researcher also provided a consent document for the study.

The data collected from the respondents would remain the most private and confidential and only be utilized for the purpose of the study. As such, the researcher had considered protecting the privacy of the respondents and others. This was done in compliance with RA 10173, also referred to as the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Results

Problem 1. What are the lived experiences of the public-school teachers who recovered from COVID-19

Theme 1. Physical Symptoms

Raw Experiences	Sub Themes	Theme	Interpretation
Experiences of Public School Teachers Who Recovered from Covid19			
P001- <i>Yun na yung may time na gusto kong matulog, hindi ako makatulog anong oras na. lambot na lambot na ko nun nung araw na yun. / Yung fever ko kasi, on and off. kaya pala ako laging nauuhaw," kasi si COVID inuubos niya pala talaga yung lahat ng fluids sa katawan mo so kaya talagang manghihina ka talaga kasi nadehydrate ka na</i>	Sleep Issues	1. Physical Symptoms	The manifestations of physical symptoms clearly are different with different people based on the accounts of the informants. One cannot generalize about physical symptoms. All these stress and lack of sleep can have big, negative impacts on the overall health of patients. One concern that is specific to the pandemic according to Dr. Drerup is the effect on our immune system. "When someone is chronically sleep-deprived," she says, "they tend to have lowered immunity and that makes our susceptibility to viruses higher." Physical symptoms like cough affect sleep patterns of the informants. Some of them have interrupted sleep and some have extended hours of sleep. One may experience one of the symptoms identified by the Center for Disease Control (CDC) and others may not, the absence of one or two of these symptoms does not mean that you do not have Covid19. CDC identifies these patients as asymptomatic. It is recommended to get tested as early as possible to avoid infecting unsuspecting people around.
P002- <i>Bale may ubo na ako na madikit sya, may lagnat ako, may back pain at diarrhea...one day lang ang lagnat ko...</i>	Fever and cough		
P005- <i>yung sakit ng ulo normal na po sa akin yun, pero bakit ako may clogged nose sa gabi?/ Eh nararamdaman ko na po na hingal na hingal na po ako. Wala po akong lagnat wala din po akong sore throat.</i>	Physical exhaustion		
P006- <i>Huwebes na dun ko talaga nafefeel na nilalagnat tinatrangaso na ako, tapos yung husband ko din tinatrangaso na</i>	Loss of smell and taste		
P007- <i>hindi po ako makapagsalita po dati kasi po bawat salita ko po dati uubuhin ako kaya po ang hirap</i>	Diarrhea		
	Feeling of thirst		
	Dehydration		

Theme 2. Social Stigma

Raw Experiences	Sub Themes	Theme	Interpretation
Experiences of Public School Teachers Who Recovered from Covid19			
P001- <i>kaso yung kapitbahay namin napansin namin na hindi dinadaan ang bahay namin, umiiwas siya.</i>	Discrimination	2. Social Stigma	The dilemma that the informants are going through is all too real.
P002- <i>So dun na nag umpisa ang problema ko kasi nga</i>	Shame		Social Stigma associated with COVID-19

mam di ba may kidney failure ako need ko ng dialysis...so hindi ako maisasalang sa dialysis center namin yung regular session ko po ay mavovoid kasi nag positive ako sa Covid19 pede ako makahawa sa ibang patients so hindi ako pede sumama,

Guilt

Dilemma

P002-That time kasi kasagsagan ng covid iniisip ko baka pandirihan ako ganun kaya yung nakalam lang yung mga close ko.

P003-Nung una sinikreto ko, sabi ko dun sa chairman namin na wag niyo munang sabihin ma'am kasi in denial pa ako sa stage na yan eh nagbasa basa rin ako, nagkwentuhan din po kami ng family ko, napagisip isip ko na bat ka mahihiya eh di mo naman kasalanan yun.

P004-Nung una kasi nakafocus ako sa wedding ko...nakasched kasi kaming ikasal ni jowa nung April 30 tapos napostponed ang wedding.

P005-Nung una po talagang nahihiya po ako di ba po yung iba binabato ang bahay binabash ka sa fb.

P006-Kung kelan kami magaling na ha...dun ko na naramdaman yan discrimination na yan... kasi nakakapag post ka na sa fb...dun mo na nababasa ang mga comments. Dyos ko po halos ipagtabuyan kami...mag pa test daw muna kami at dalhin namin ang result na negative kami...na upset talaga ako...kaya umuwi nalang kaming mag asawa.

P008-Kailangan ipaalam pala naming dito sa homeowners na may positive rito sa subdivision naming. Pinaalam na sa City government of Antipolo para masundo na kami. So nung una talagang ayaw kong magpadala sa isolation facility.

is fueling harmful stereotypes with Covid19 recoveries. How does it affect the person with Covid19? "Social stigma in the context of health is the negative association between a person or group of people who share certain characteristics and a specific disease. In an outbreak, this may mean people are labelled, stereotyped, discriminated against, treated separately, and/or experience loss of status because of a perceived link with a disease. Stigma can drive people to hide the illness to avoid discrimination, prevent people from seeking health care immediately, discourage them from adopting healthy behaviors and most of all miss out on major life events.

Problem 2. How did the respondents describe their experiences in terms of emotional and mental conditions?

Theme 3: Fear of the Unknown

Raw Experiences	Sub Themes	Theme	Interpretation
Experiences of Public School Teachers Who Recovered from Covid19			
P001-Akala ko ano lang siya, simpleng lagnat lang madali siyang macure. Pero as time goes by, narealize ko na hindi pala siya basta basta, yung inaakala ng marami na basta trangkaso, hindi po pala siya ganun. Inisip ko agad ma'am pano yung trabaho ko, pano yung mga bata, pano ko magagampanan yung responsibilities ko. Nakatulog ako sa sobrang lungkot sa sobrang worry nung unang araw ko na nalaman na positive ako para sa family ko. Paano kung nahawaan ko sila? Pano si mother ko na diabetic pano yung tita ko na senior na tapos meron ding comorbidities. May effect si COVID na parang meron pa kahit wala naman na. Parang medyo napapraning ka na.	Stress	3. Fear of the Unknown	Stress is commonplace they say with or without Covid 19. Anxiety is often defined as the fear of the unknown. This feeling of uncertainty and lack of control over our environment can put us on edge, impact our moods, affect our relationships, and cloud our thinking. The world we thought we knew has changed dramatically. This Covid19 can be very anxiety provoking and it is how many of the informants described their experience. During this crisis it is important to grieve what has been lost, and it is also important to find meaning and hope in how life has changed us. We must find a WHY to live during this unsettling time. traumatic stress or what is known as Post Traumatic Stress Syndrome (PTSD) is a problem not only of remembering the past, but also of anticipating the future. Fear of the unknown triggers all the mental and emotional instability of all the informants. It is very evident in their accounts of the ordeal that they went through.
	Anxiety		
	Trauma		
	Grief		
P003-Nagtalo talaga kami. Sabi ko san ko ba nakuha to eh bumibili lang naman ako rito ma'am eh lagi ko namang ginagawa yun. Sana ako nalang wag na yung anak ko kasi bata pa eh tsaka may mga time na umiiyak siya pag gabi. Parang wala ka ng pagasa parang ganun. Sabi ko, wala na ba kaming pagasa, bakit ganto yung nangyari sa buhay namin.	Hopelessness		Fear or anxiety can be brought about both by knowing or having more information and by fear of the unknown related to the virus. In fact, an uncertain and continuous threat can become chronic and burdensome with many infected people being asymptomatic, the rate of infections are impossible
P004-meron pa namang mga plema ngayon actually eh, may sipon pa rin ako hanggang			

ngayon. Tsaka nasa isip ko pa rin eh, traumatized ako. May quarentine facility po sa barangay nag stay po ako ng one night. Dinala po ako ng ambulansya sa hospital ng Cabading at nagpa lab test. Sabi ko dun Sir wala po talaga akong pera...tinatanong ako ng doktor kung hirap akong huminga...nakakastress po yung gastusin.

to calculate and there is no way for a person to know if the other next to him is infected or not, adding more uncertainty to the situation. The unknown triggers the fear and fear triggers anxiety.

P008-All members of my family were infected. In 2 weeks' time, we lost two members of the family, my mother who is 84 years old and a brother, who is 56 years old. *Grieving talaga kami sa magkasunod na pagkamatay ng Nanay at kapatid ko dahil sa Covid19.*

Problem 3. How did the respondents cope with Covid19?

Theme 4: Trust and Support

Raw Experiences	Sub Themes	Theme	Interpretation
Experiences of Public School Teachers Who Recovered from Covid19			
P001- <i>Meron akong pinsan na health worker na medtech so siya yung nagmomonitor siya lang yung lumalapit talaga sa akin.</i>			Recovery is a personal journey with the goals of hope, empowerment and autonomy. Many factors contribute to recovery, including having a good support system of people that you like, respect and trust. Research has shown that having a social support system can have a positive impact on one's overall mental health. Stress level for people with emotional support in place
P002- <i>May best friend ako halos 6 hours kami magkausap sa phone. Kinocomfort nya ako... pag nag end ang call naiiyak ako kasi alone na naman ako parang ganun...naghahanap ka ng friend...yung katabi ko malala kaya di ko naman makausap ginagawa ko nalang kinakausap ko yung mga nurse...</i>			
P003- <i>Sa akin, napahinga talaga yung buong katawan ko... wala akong masabi sa aking chairman, supportive naman sila. May binigay naman sila sa amin na financial assistance.</i>	Support Groups	4. Trust and Support	All hands-on deck or Bayanihan is a wonderful thing in this pandemic to give support in however and whatever ways. This part of the study is the most important part because it showed how the informant's resiliency were manifested in many different ways with the support and assistance by people and colleagues.
<i>pinanood ko nun ma'am mga cartoons na pinapanood ko nung bata ako. Parang bumalik ako sa panahon dati na ganiito ako dati ang saya-saya. Makinig ka rin sa music na nakakarela ka. Tapos minsan kapag may Mass. Naka monitor lagi yung doktor sa akin</i>	Nourishments		
	Health Protocols		
	Beautiful Distractions		
P004- <i>Madali kang mapagod lagi lang akong nakahiga natutulong...tapos yung mga aso sila ang nagpapasaya sa araw ko... dapat di ko sila kasama pero ayaw nila akong lubayan... Dinaan ko sa kain... Vit. C tutulog kakain Vit. C kaya tumaba... Tulog ako nang tulog 12-16 hours... Ikinain ko nalang anxiety ko</i>	Strong Faith in God		Beautiful distractions like food, pets, humor, cartoons, fb, music and most of all the internet, this has become the lifeline to those in isolation like those in the quarantine facilities, the internet has become a necessity often it is the only way recovering patients can connect with the outside world.
P005- <i>Yung check up at lab test sinagot po ni Kapitan. tinatawagan ako n mga kumare ko. nagpapanata ako sa gabi. Malaking bagay yung may sumusuporta sayo.</i>			
P006- <i>Puro steam, hot water , ginger tea with lemon araw araw at gulay...nagtatanim ako ng gulay exercise na din.</i>			Another important idea that emerged in the data is the relationship between doctors and patients. The relationship must be built on TRUST, patient believing the medical expert and medical expert listening to the patient.
P007- <i>Yung newborn son ko, sya ang nagpapalakas ng loob ko.</i>			

Problem 4. How did the respondents describe their state of being after they survived Covid19?

Theme 5: Indomitable Will to Survive

Raw Experiences	Sub Themes	Theme	Interpretation
Experiences of Public School Teachers Who Recovered from Covid19			

<p>P001-Parang kinaya ko nalang din siya. Kinailangan ko na talagang tanggapin na hindi na kami pwede magsabaysabay kumain. wag po sana nating itago o ikahiya ang pagkakaroon ng Covid.</p>		<p>Indomitable will to survive is the penultimate theme in this study. Informants are more vigilant and cautious.</p>
<p>P002-Ako kasi accepted ko na sya lalaban ako alam ko naman sa sarili ko kaya ko pero paano yung mga kasama ko pano kung di nila kaya Kailangan maging handa tayo. Positive lang ako sa attitude ko ngayon.</p>		<p>Defensive behaviors are triggered by activity in survival that detects imminent threats. Fear is the conscious emotion brought about by the threat of Covid19. This mysterious disease is triggering anxieties much more than fear. It presented as a significant occupational hazard to public school teachers who continuously and diligently fulfill their mandates. Their economic consequences also have a psychological impact of when told to remain in their houses and work from home but is still required to report because of the nature of their jobs. How do we survive this pandemic? They ask. Where do we get the money for treatment if infected, they ask? “Survival comes from within says one of the respondents. She has surrendered herself to the Lord, found support in her faith in God. She just stopped asking questions and just surrendered herself to the Lord. Death never crossed her mind because of the confidence that she will be saved by her strong will to survive. Optimism got the better of her.</p>
<p>P004-Thankful ako...Nagpapasalamat ako kay Lord kasi favored pa rin ako kasi hindi ako namatay. sinabi ko kay Lord na alam ko na di ko pa time...na sya na ang bahala wala naman akong magagawa...meds cannot help me, no vits no exercise na makapagsalba sa akin kundi si Lord lang...</p>	<p>Strong will Surrender to God Acceptance and Realizations</p>	<p>5. Indomitable Will to Survive</p>
<p>P006-Siguro yang Covid andyan na yan makakasama na natin yan araw araw. sakaling babalikan man ako ni Covid siguro mas handa na ako...sa isip at lalo na sa financialna pangangailanagan kung saka sakali man.Hindi makakatulong kung magpapanick ka...</p>	<p>Speaking Up</p>	
<p>P007-Hopeful po ako... ayaw ko pong lumala magkasakit lalo kasi gusto ko pong makita ang baby ko at maalagaan ang asawa ko sa ospital. Dasal po ang almusal ko tanghalian at hapunan ko ngayon.</p>		
<p>P008-Pinilit kong kumain kahit wala akong gana para mabuhay ako. Talagang nasa atin ang susi upang labanan ang Covid na ito...palakasin natin ang ating mga katawan.</p>		

Problem 5. What intervention can be recommended by this study that can mitigate the health crisis brought by COVID-19 pandemic?

Mitigating Behaviors	Plan of Action	HBD Model- Cues to Action Internal/External	Sample Priority Response
Preparation	Establish a task force or steering committee that will have responsibility to develop and implement the education response to the COVID-19 Pandemic.	Perceived Benefits	Establish mechanisms of coordination with public health authorities so that education actions are in synch and help advance public health goals and strategies, for example, educating students, parents, teachers and staff on the necessity for social distancing and hygiene.
Coping	Physical/Medical Support	Perceived Barriers	The incubation period for this disease is generally one to fourteen (1-14) days, hence isolation for at least fourteen days (14) right after having been tested COVID-19 positive should be immediate and strictly followed without question as a matter of protocol for all.
	Mental/Emotional Support	Perceived Barriers	Schools must provide social services, such as mental health supports and develop other alternative forms of provisions.
	Financial and logistical support	Perceived Barriers	Ensure that school leaders get the financial, logistical and moral support they need to succeed and execute necessary protocols. Each school should develop a plan for continuity of operations. As a way to support them, education authorities can provide curated examples of plans in other schools.
Recovery		Self-efficacy	Ex. Wellness (Physical and breathing exercise) that can help teachers improve their immune system.

Discussion

The eight public school teachers who were the informants or participants of the study experienced a myriad of situations that gave them challenging circumstances in their quest to survive from the pandemic, COVID-19, during the year 2020-2021. The overarching themes and their subthemes, which emerged from the data analysis are as follows: Theme 1: Physical Symptoms; Theme 2: Social Stigma; Theme 3: Fear of the unknown; Theme 4: Trust and Support; and Theme 5: Indomitable will to survive.

The rest of this Chapter discussed these themes through the words and responses of the informants/participants themselves. This chapter also detailed how these themes fit into the broader conceptual framework of the research study namely the Health Belief Model (HBM) developed in 1950s by social psychologists of the US Public Health Service and remains one of the best known and widely used theories in health behavior research. Another framework used in this study is A. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs which covers human's basic needs such as (a) Physiological, (b) Safety, (c) Social, (d) Esteem and (e) Self-actualization.

The results of this study added a perspective to the recovered teachers from COVID-19 Pandemic by sharing their experiences during their time of medication or treatment up to the period when they recovered from the unseen virus. One of the researcher's reasons in conducting the study is to find out how the public-school teachers who were tested COVID-19 positive were able to cope with the pains brought by the present pandemic, how did they hurdle their finances during the period of isolation, treatment and moreover their physical, emotional and mental health issues and problems.

The interviews revealed that; COVID-19 affects different people in different ways, as physical symptoms existed and were experienced by the informants like sleep issues, fever and cough, physical exhaustion, loss of smell and taste, diarrhea, feeling of thirst and dehydration. The World Health Organization, (WHO, 2020) stated that "COVID-19 gives varying effects to different hosts. One may experience one of the symptoms, while others may have two or three manifestations. One host may be severely symptomatic while some maybe asymptomatic, where the host does not feel any symptoms at all, however the COVID-19 is in his body system. WHO and IATF have provided guidance and precautions on how one can be safe from being contaminated by the invisible virus.

The second question on how the participants of the study describe their physical, emotional and mental state being revealed that they experienced; discrimination shame/embarrassment, guilt and dilemma. The impact of COVID-19 has brought them to social isolation and extreme loneliness. They missed out some important family events and celebrations. Their experiences have caused them to hide the illness to avoid discrimination.

Moreover, anxiety, trauma, grief, hopelessness are considered unknown fear which emerged during the interview. One common experience shared by the informants was traumatic stress syndrome (PTSD), a problem not only of remembering the past, but also of anticipating the future. Traumatic stress symptoms because of COVID-19 were experienced by the informants because of their direct exposure to previous events that were threatening like death, severe pain, injury and others. The research findings support emerging research that COVID-19 can be regarded as a traumatic stressor event capable of eliciting PTSD-like responses and aggravating other related mental health problems (Bridgl and et.al., 2020).

On the coping strategies during quarantine emerged these following accounts from the eight informants: (a) support groups, (b) nourishments, (c) following health protocols, (d) beautiful distractions and (e) strong faith to God. The informants got engaged to beautiful distractions like gardening, tending to their pets, listening to music, viewing television programs, making friendly thoughts through Facebook/social media made their social isolation less lonely. Likewise, work, relationships and building trust among the frontliners, nurse and doctors gave them wonderful experiences in the facility and/or hospitals. Accordingly, the informants shared that the first and foremost pain-reliever that they had and met at the midst of their loneliness was God Almighty. And to state the words of P004, "COVID is just a name, there is more powerful name and that is the name of Jesus... Find comfort in the Lord."

The fourth and last interview-question has a tint of the participants'/ informants' behavior after their experience with COVID-19. Their responses have a solid hope of winning their lives and the lives of their loved-ones from the unseen COVID-19. Strong will to survive, coupled with strong faith of winning the battle against the pandemic got them through and recovered from COVID-19.

Conclusion

At this point, the study has come up with the following conclusions: (1) Epidemiology and clinical characteristics of COVID-19. The incubation period for this disease is generally one to fourteen (1-14) days, hence the informants of the study got isolated for at least fourteen days (14) right after having been tested COVID-19 positive. The disease usually begins with respiratory symptoms described as fever and cough for two to three (2-3) days. The informants experienced the given symptoms which confirmed that COVID-19 causes upper respiratory disease and immune responses. (WHO, 2019).

The (2) second conclusion is on physical activity and mental health of the eight teacher-informants during their treatment period due to COVID-19. Accordingly, they experienced social stigma, fear, anxiety, trauma, grief and hopelessness while they were in isolation at the quarantine facility or in the hospital. It can be deduced that lockdown and isolation with respect to their mental health and their relationship in three (3) main fields: work, facility and social relationships and physical activities have strong relationship with distress due to adjustments during lockdown and quarantines, (Asmundson and Taylor, 2020) worry, panic, anxiety, depression and stress levels, impaired sleep and low physical activities or mobility put their enthusiasm at its lowest.

The (3) third conclusion is that teachers are very resilient, they believe that events are controlled by external forces and humans have no power over them and can no longer influence them; and they are considered greatly as barriers to screening and preventive behaviors. Preventive behaviors from COVID-19 in the present study using the Health Belief Model (HBM), self-efficacy is defined as the level of trust and confidence in overcoming barriers to a healthy behavior. HBD goes on to say that individuals should have an appropriate level of self-efficacy to overcome barriers to behavior.

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